

KNOWLEDGE ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE REGARDING MEDICATION ADMINISTRATION RIGHTS AMONG NURSES WORKING IN PUBLIC SECTOR HOSPITALS OF SWAT PAKISTAN

Mujahid Ullah^{*1}, Yaser Ud-din²

^{*1,2}Royal College of Nursing, Khyber Medical University Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, 19200 Pakistan

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Corresponding Author: *

Mujahid Ullah

Abstract

Background: The six rights for nurses when giving medication are known as medication administration rights (MARs). Nurses must administer the medication correctly to the right patient, in the correct dose, through the correct route, at the right time, and document it appropriately. Following these rights ensures patient safety and prevents medication errors. Medication errors are a significant

problem in healthcare, harming patients, increasing costs, and lowering the quality of care. Nurses' knowledge, attitude, and practice are crucial in medication administration to prevent errors and improve patient safety. Adhering to medication administration rights is essential for secure and effective medication delivery. Nurses play a critical role in upholding these rights and ensuring safe and effective care for patients. Their attitudes and practices can be influenced by factors such as workload, staffing levels, and organizational culture. Incorrect administration or ineffective medication can lead to serious harm or even death for patients.

Aim of the study: The current study was carried out to assess the knowledge, attitude, and practice of nurses toward medication administration rights, and identify the factors that influence the adherence to these rights such as education, training, experience, workload, and organizational culture.

Design: A descriptive cross-sectional study design was used.

Setting: The study was conducted on nurses in public sector hospitals.

Subjects: 160 nurses were selected from two public sector hospitals of Swat KPK Pakistan.

Tools: Three tools were used, the first tool was used to assess the knowledge of nurses toward medication administration rights, the second tool was used for assessing the attitude, and the third tool was used to assess the skills practice of nurses toward medication administration.

Findings: The study found that most nurses were aged 30-40, had a BS Nursing degree, and had 5-10 years of experience. It also found that nurses had good knowledge (78.6%) and rarely made errors (22.4%) in drug administration rights, with the most common errors being wrong dose and wrong timing. Nurses generally (54.2%) had a positive attitude towards medication administration rights but were hesitant to report errors. The study

emphasizes the importance of positive attitudes and error reporting to improve patient well-being and reduce errors. It is also found that more than three-quarters (76.4%) of the nurses have good practice and follow proper administration skills. However, (23.6%) have poor practice and do not follow proper skills.

Conclusion: Most nurses have good knowledge, practice, and a positive attitude toward medication administration rights. However, some nurses had poor practice and a negative

attitude toward reporting errors, which needs to be improved by continuous education, training, experience, reduced workload, and positive organizational culture.

Introduction:

The set of six rights that nurses must follow when administering medication is known as medication administration rights (MARs), as stated by the World Health Organization (WHO). This involves administering the medication correctly to the right patient, in the correct dose,

through the correct route, at the right time, and that documentation is completed appropriately.

Patient safety and prevention of medication errors are ensured by these rights. Errors in medication are major health problems in healthcare, harming patients, driving up expenses, and lowering the standard of treatment. Nurses' roles are very critical in medication

administration, and their knowledge, attitude, and practice are essential in medication

administration To prevent medication errors and improve patient safety.[23] The concept of

medication administration rights is essential for nurses to understand and adhere to ascertain

secure and efficacious medication dispensation.

Nurses' knowledge of giving drugs to the patient rights is essential to preventing medication errors.

They play a critical role in ensuring that medication administration rights are upheld and that patients receive safe and effective care.

Nurses' attitudes can influence their behavior and adherence to medication administration

rights lastly the Nurses' practice can be influenced by their knowledge and attitude, as well as other

factors such as workload, staffing levels, and organizational culture. When a patient is

administered incorrectly or receive ineffective pharmacological therapy medication error

happen. The patient may die as a result of fetal

errors brought on by improper medication administration. [1]

Around 1.5 million people are affected annually by medication errors, which is a worldwide problem. [2] World Health

Organization defined drug administration errors as "any preventable event that may cause or lead to inappropriate medication use or patient harm while the medication is in the control of the healthcare professional, patient, or consumer."

At any phase of medication method, mistakes in medications can occur but many of them happen when administering medications. [3] A vital role is

played by nurses in medication administration, Prevention of medication errors is essential, and

This can be attained by utilizing the knowledge, attitude, and practice of nurses regarding the rights of medication administration. The

fundamental principles of administering medication are the "six rights" that nurses must follow to ensure safe and effective medication

administration. [4] However, studies have shown that nurses' knowledge,

attitude, and practice toward medication administration rights are often inadequate,

leading to medication errors and patient harm. In Pakistan, medication errors are a significant

problem, with studies reporting high rates of medication errors in hospitals. [5] 3.6% of

errors in medication

orders, with administration errors being the most common type of error have been reported

in public sector hospitals in Lahore Pakistan. [6] Administration errors constitute the most

prevalent

category of medication errors, which account for 46.1% of the reported errors in medication orders.

[4] World Health Organization (WHO) reports that medication errors and unsafe practices are one of the major causes of patient harm in the healthcare system worldwide. These errors cost the healthcare system more than \$42 billion USD every year and result in an estimated 2 million deaths worldwide. [7] Studies have

found that nurses may lack knowledge about medication administration rights and that this can contribute to errors. Attitudes and beliefs about medication administration rights may also play a role in medication errors. [8] Some studies have found that nurses may not feel empowered to speak up about medication errors or may be hesitant to question physicians or other healthcare providers. [9] In order to improve medication safety and reduce errors, interventions such as education and training programs, the use of technology, and improved communication and collaboration among healthcare providers have been suggested. [10]

Swat is a district in the province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in Pakistan, as on the KP-BOIT website, With an estimated populace of around 2.3 million individuals. The district has a total of 11 public- sector hospitals, namely

1. Saidu Teaching Hospital
2. Nawaz sharif kidney Teaching hospital Manglawar, Swat
3. Kabal Tehsil Headquarter Hospital
4. Matta Tehsil Headquarter Hospital
5. Khwaza Khela Tehsil Headquarter Hospital
6. Barikot Tehsil Headquarter Hospital
7. Charbagh Tehsil Headquarter Hospital
8. Bahrain Tehsil Headquarter Hospital
9. Kalam Tehsil Headquarter Hospital
10. Madyan Tehsil Headquarter Hospital
11. Chakdara District headquarter hospital

Providing healthcare services to the local population. However, there is limited research on nurses' understanding, perspective, and Procedure toward medication administration rights in public sector hospitals in swat Pakistan.

1.2 The broad Purpose of the Research

This research has aims to evaluate Nurses' understanding, behavior, & approach toward the six medication administration rights. The study will examine the factors that affect the nurses' understanding, attitude, & practice toward drug administration, such as education, training, experience, workload, and organizational culture.

The study's findings will contribute to identifying the areas that require improvement. The significance of the study is that by understanding nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding medication administration rights, healthcare organizations can develop interventions to improve patient safety and reduce

medication errors. Overall, the study can of medication administration rights.

- To assess the attitudes of nurses towards medication administration rights.
- To evaluate the practices of nurses in relation to medication administration rights.

Literature Review

The articles in this study were obtained from various sources, including online resources such as Google Scholar, PubMed, ResearchGate, Medicare, NCBI, Publications, Internal sources, and CourseHero, as well as journals and books.

The aim of this literature review is to analyze the present understanding, beliefs, and behaviors of nurses working in public sector hospitals in Swat, Pakistan regarding medication administration rights. Medication administration is a crucial aspect of nursing practice, and medication errors can have serious consequences for patients. Therefore, it is essential to understand the determinants that impact the nurses understanding, behavior & practices regarding drug administration rights. The review will provide an overview of the research conducted on this topic and explore the factors that influence nurses' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding medication administration rights. The review will identify gaps in the current research and provide recommendations for improving nurses understanding, attitudes, & practices concerning drug administration rights.

Comprehensive overview:

Administering medication is a complex process

that demands high skill and knowledge. Nurses are responsible for guaranteeing that medications are administered to patients safely and effectively. The knowledge, attitudes, and practices of nurses concerning medication administration rights are critical aspects of patient safety. [12]

The World health organization (WHO) has defined A series of regulations and protocols that healthcare professionals must strictly follow in order to guarantee the utmost safety and effective delivery of medication to patients. These guidelines include guaranteeing that the medication remains given to the appropriate individual, in the accurate quantity, via the precise method, at the designated moment, and that documentation is completed appropriately.

It falls under the responsibilities of nurses to guarantee drugs administration rights are respected. They should possess knowledge about the medications they are administering, which includes nursing interventions, indications, contraindications, side effects, and interactions. Furthermore, they should be acquainted with the protocols for administering medications, which include the correct dose, route, and timing of administration

The attitudes of nurses concerning medication administration rights are significant. They must be dedicated to ensuring that patients get the correct medication, in the appropriate quantity, through the suitable pathway, at the appropriate moment, and that documentation is adequately completed. They must also be willing to speak up and advocate for patients if they believe that medication administration rights are being violated.

The practices of nurses regarding medication administration rights are of utmost importance to patient safety. They should be careful in administering medications, paying close attention to the medication orders, Ensuring the administration of suitable medication to the correct recipient, in the precise dosage, via the appropriate pathway, at the designated moment, and meticulously completing documentation.

In last If healthcare providers don't have enough knowledge, skills, or the right attitude towards medication administration rights, it can lead to

medication errors that can have serious consequences for patients. Therefore, it's important that nurses receive adequate training and education on medication administration rights and that they are supported in their practice by their employers and colleagues.

Literature

During a study from March 1 to April 30, 2018, among 422 nurses in public hospitals, their knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding medication administration were evaluated. The findings showed that most nurses had good understanding and adherence to medication administration rights. there were gaps in their attitudes towards medication administration rights. The study recommends continuous education and training programs for nurses to improve their attitudes toward medication administration rights.[12]

One of the cross-sectional study was conducted on the understanding, attitudes, & practices of nurses regarding drug administration rights in the tertiary care hospital in India among 150 nurses using a structured questionnaire. The results showed that the majority of the respondents had good knowledge (87.3%) and practice (89.3%) regarding medication administration rights.

However, only 48.7% of the respondents had a favorable outlook when it came to administering medication. The study recommends continuous education and training programs for nurses to improve their attitudes toward medication administration rights. In contrast, This research found that 22.4% of nurses made a medication error in the past year. Most nurses (78.6%) have good knowledge about medication rights and (76.4%) follow proper administration skills. However, (23.6%) do not follow proper skills. Additionally, (24.5%) have a positive attitude toward reporting errors, while (17%) have a negative attitude.

It has been found by a study at Mansura University Egypt that the well-being and safety of the patients is of utmost importance to healthcare organizations globally. The challenges that nurse face when administering medication to patients must be recognized. The research was carried out

on a group of 140 nurses, and the results showed that less than 66% of them had inadequate overall score of knowledge when it comes to medication administration. A positive attitude towards medication administration was held by slightly more than half of the nurses, while more than two-fifths had a negative attitude. Low overall score when it comes to the practice of medication administration were observed in around 50% of the nurses. A statistically notable correlation was observed between the understanding, execution, and mindset of nurses regarding drugs dispensation. Furthermore, Nurses' understanding of drugs administration showed a statistically significant association with their level of expertise gained over time. Additionally, a statistically significant association was observed between nurses' practice in drugs administration and their sex and qualification. In their study, Asim and Nagy (2007) found that there were significant differences in the responses of participants based on their years of experience and current clinical working area regarding the likelihood of medication errors. However, the nurses' years of experience did not appear to influence understanding or expertise, but it did affect their attitude. The study's findings indicated that nurses possess inadequate understandings, insufficient practice, and unfavorable attitudes towards drug administration, necessitating rectification. The suggestions proposed by the study's results are straightforward informational materials like pamphlets and leaflets regarding medication administration fundamental guidance and medication mishaps should be created and disseminated in all healthcare environments.

Empirically-supported medication administration protocols should be incorporated into the curriculum of pharmacology courses for nursing students. Using a standardized evaluation form to assess the caliber of knowledge, attitude, and practices regarding medication administration is advisable. The implementation of a protocol that promotes the reporting of medication errors without punitive measures should be considered. Incorporating instructional and educational workshops as components of an in-service

training initiative is recommended. [14]

A study has shown in referral hospitals in Ethiopia Patients can be harmed by medication errors, confidence in healthcare system can be threatened, therapeutic interventions can be induced, patients' hospitalization can be prolonged, extra costs can be produced, and death can even result from medication errors. Medication administration errors (MAE) were assessed through the research that was conducted and associated factors among nurses in Ethiopian referral hospitals were assessed in the study. A total of 422 participants were selected. In this research MAE transpired by 57.7% of the subjects, with over thrice of recurrence by 30.4% of them. Erroneous timing, imprecise appraisal, and unsuitable evaluation were the most prevalent medication administration errors perpetrated. A conspicuous association between medication administration errors and inadequate training and the dearth of guidelines was discerned. [15]

A study has found in Sik Hospital Kedah, Malaysia which investigated A majority of the nurses (54%) manifested a moderate level of knowledge in medication administration, while 46%

evinced a high level, and none of them possessed a low level. Another study found that the subjects' years of expertise and present clinical working domain affected their reactions to medication errors. The differences were statistically significant. [34] Nonetheless, the knowledge and practice of nurses, except for their attitude, were not influenced by the years of expertise.

The questionnaire was accomplished by a total of 48 respondents, resulting in a response rate of 100%. A good level of knowledge about medication was possessed by the respondents. Heavy workload and complex orders, which accounted for 95.8% of the cases, were the main factors contributing to medication errors. The second most significant factor was the percentage of new staff at 81.2% and personnel who were neglected at 66%. The findings revealed that medication errors were affected by various factors. The primary causes encompassed a heavy

workload, complex orders, and the presence of new staff. [16]

A study located that Pakistani nurses have negative know-how of excessive alert medications (HAMs) administration and law, with around eighty four% of examine participants achieving scores <70%. Foremost limitations encountered in the course of HAMs management have been “getting unsure answers from colleagues” (72.Nine%), “unavailability of a appropriate individual to seek advice from” (61.1%), and “receiving verbal orders” (fifty five.6%). It is critical for nurses to acquire comprehensive pharmacology knowledge not only at some point of in-school nursing education however also in sanatorium-based persevering with schooling. [17] Studies have found that Essential nursing processes used to administer medications safely are not recognized by the literature, which often focuses on medication errors. The five to 10 regulations of drugs administration protection that nurses comply with are studied, although administering medications is a more comprehensive role than rule-following. Proactive use of critical thinking skills is Utilized by nurses to evaluate a customer's fame and needs and to apprehend complications and medicine mistakes. In-depth knowledge and evaluation of the patient's situation and activities that have an effect on the affected person are required with the aid of the nurse's decision-making to manipulate medications, and interventions based on clinical reasoning are used to make certain sufferers receive medicinal drugs competently. Clinical reasoning is required by safe medication administration Previous to, during, and following affected person interventions. The studies worried 326 nurses from different hospital units and community

settings. The nurses' knowledge of medicines and important wondering procedures had been confirmed with the aid of their movements of administering and double-checking medicines. The literature reviewed medication administration in healthcare organizations with a focus on nurses' avoidance of medication errors. It have been provided basis for the three stages of addressing medication errors: identifying them,

interrupting (questioning) them, and correcting them. The research identified commonplace techniques used by nurses to ensure affected person protection, such as looking for explanation of medication orders and contacting other colleagues and physicians with whom that they had a great working dating. Organizational factors, along with the tradition of safety and a nurse's choice to impeach medicinal drug management, have been located to influence drug errors.[18]

Another study has been reviewed which is carried out in Queen Rania St, Amman, Jordan university hospital in which Nurses' perceptions closer to medicine administration mistakes (MAEs) reporting have been evaluated, and factors contributing to below-reporting of errors have been recognized. It was found that nurses had a high-quality mindset towards reporting MAEs, however, the primary reason for under-reporting was nursing administration concerns. Factors that contribute to the under-reporting of MAEs, such as personal fear of reporting errors, lack of time, lack of knowledge, and fear of embarrassment from colleagues and managers, were identified. The need for continuous education programs to promote proper reporting of MAEs and The need for powerful and confined guidelines in non-punishing surroundings to prevent MAE incidents were emphasized in the study. [19]

Nurses play A crucial function in drug administration, being the final checkpoint to ensure correct prescription and dispensation. The ‘five prerogatives’ of medication dispensation, which is a criterion to clinical medication allocation and maintaining patient security, are instructed to learners throughout the education of nursing. These prerogatives were established during an epoch when providers were solely responsible for any errors, and patients had little participation in their own care. The conventional structure for instructing the ‘five prerogatives’ has not culminated in a considerable diminution in error ratios since its introduction. the 'five rights' have been criticized for relying solely on them, lacking consideration for the patient's role, and the need for additional rights. Contemporary

inquiries have detected deficiencies of the 'five prerogatives' in diminishing errors owing to workplace pressures on nursing personnel, workload, understaffing, or disruptions. Nurses may have difficulty finding specific warnings on pharmaceutical labeling and packaging, particularly in inadequately illuminated surroundings. The ascertaining of novel products being user-friendly is the accountability of pharmaceutical fabricators and governing and regulation establishments.^[20]

It is stated in the literature that the responsibility of the 'five rights' is not only for nurses but also for the entire healthcare organization to ensure functionality. The unique responsibilities of all healthcare workers are required to ensure medication dispensation security and conformity to the five prerogatives because medical errors are interprofessional. Responses from the drugstore or

the doctor should be sought by nurses. If there are any inquiries regarding the understanding of the prescription, the medication, or the dosage, instead of blindly following prescriber orders. Equipping experts with sufficient time and resources to protect patients, which is not invariably feasible without manifold workplace disruptions, is the best way for nurses to fulfill their responsibility.^[21]

One of the medicinal literature accentuates that the importance of nurses' logical thinking, the role of patient advocating, and healthcare evaluation are not recognized by the five prerogatives structures, which are extensively utilized in modern practice to dispense patient-centered care. A distinct advantage in decision-making capability has been shown to be provided by nursing experience, but further studies are needed to better understand how intuition is applied, the context of the situation is interpreted, and decisions are made by nurses. According to a 2002 survey, it is believed by approximately 36% of patients that deliberation concerning care and interventions should be a mutual accountability. Roughly fifty percent of patients perceive themselves as primarily accountable for decision-making. This survey underscores the escalating significance of patients'

decision-making aptitude, which introduces a fresh element to a "checks and balances" framework that holds promise in enhancing patient safety during medication dispensation.^[22]

Another published paper has been reviewed titled "The nine rights of medication administration: an overview" in which we found that drug errors are prevalent in the context of patient care.

High-quality, safe, and evidence-based care should be delivered by nurses, with patient safety and care quality being the top priorities in all clinical situations. However, this can be challenging in certain circumstances, such as obscurity during the graveyard shift or a trio of

admissions in quick succession to a hectic ward, which can create an environment that increases the possibility of errors. The work environment should be managed by nurses to reduce the likelihood of making mistakes. A critical role in preventing medication errors is played by nurses, as these can occur in various stages of the administration process. The correct drug form and response should be administered by nurses, in conjunction with adhering to the established seven rights, to enhance the well-being of the patient. The compilation of drug entitlements can assist nurses in fulfilling their crucial function in ensuring patient safety, although this compilation is not all-encompassing. Regular educational sessions for staff, covering medications commonly ordered in that specific clinical field and recommended guidelines on medication administration, should be conducted by hospitals. The suggested protocols on medication dispensation, like conducting a triple verification of the medication prior to, during, and subsequent to administration, should be followed by nurses. Departures from a doctor's directive are defined as medication errors, but what has been ordered should not be blindly followed by nurses.^[3]

Another literature found that the quintessential principles of drug dispensation, have guided nurses in the realm of both academia and professional application, spanning numerous decades of enduring prominence. However, the five rights have been found to be inadequate by

many, and various rights have been proposed to be added, From the correct indication for the privileges of nurses to own readable accurate requests and prompt availability of information. Greater roles are being played by patients in the process of care, and they are no longer inert beneficiaries of care. to accost systems of care in a cooperative patient-centered milieu, an eloquent-collaborative paradigm is needed, in which entities bargain with one another to ascertain what people necessitate to discern and scheme on the expedients to procure the requisite information.

Healthcare professionals are not required anymore to possess omniscient knowledge. In conclusion, medication dispensation is not merely the five rights but a procedure with many interrelated actors, including patients. In this epoch, all implicated in the procedure partake the accountability for a secure medication utilization system that needs to be collaboratively restructured.[4] Another inquiry discovered that medication blunders in critical care are highly pervasive and unreported. The bulk of nurses in ten critical care segments at a large erudite acute care infirmary in Rhode Island had no cognizance of the infirmary's protocol or the official explication of a

medication lapse as espoused by the facility Numerous practitioners were oblivious to the fact that close-call occurrences are regarded as pharmacological blunders. the investigation implies that crucial care practitioners and their clientele would profit from augmented instruction

schemes aimed at bridging these cognition lacunae. Critical care nurses need more education & support to improve medication safety. The study found that crucial care nurses lack knowledge & education regarding the delineation, acknowledgment, and infirmary regulation protocols regarding drug errors. The ultimate objective of augmented instruction schemes would be an escalation in lucidity regarding pharmacological blunders in crucial care units, fewer pharmacological blunders, ameliorated clientele outcomes/gratification, safer pharmacological administration,

shorter/safer ICU sojourns, and increased ICU practitioner confidence and gratification. APRNs can affect and influence systems by adopting and supporting evidenced based practices, policies, and protocols for safe pharmacological management. [6]

Summary

Medication administration is a complex process that requires high skill and knowledge. Responsibility for ensuring that medications are administered safely and effectively lies with nurses. The rights of medication administration have been defined by the world health organization as a state of guidelines that must be followed by healthcare providers to ensure the safe and effective delivery of medication to patients. Knowledge about the medications being administered and protocols for administering them should be possessed by nurses. The significance of the attitudes of nurses concerning medication administration rights is that they must be willing to speak up and advocate for patients if they believe that medication administration rights are being violated. The practices of nurses regarding medication administration rights are of utmost importance to patient safety. Medication errors that can have serious consequences for patients can occur if healthcare providers lack knowledge, skills, or the right attitude towards medication administration rights.

Materials & Methodology

Research methodology is a blueprint of study used by the researcher to find the answer of the research problem in a systematic way under study. This involves all the steps that took place throughout the process of this study. It accentuates the universal schema of systematizing the modus operandi of accruing veracious and dependable evidence for an inquiry..

This chapter includes the subheadings such as study methods, setting of the research, sampling technique, sample size, inclusion & exclusion criteria. Furthermore, it deals with data collection, data analysis procedure, and ethical considerations to protect the rights of study

participants.

Subjects:

The participants of this study consisted of 160 permanent nursing staff who were the respondents to the Questionnaire, all working in public sector hospitals (Saidu Group of teaching hospital and Nawaz Sharif Kidney Hospital) Swat KPK Pakistan. This group comprised 80 female nurses (50%) and 60 male nurses (50%). The subjects work in all Hospital units: intensive care unit, operating theater, medical units, surgical units, obstetrical units, pediatric units, casualty unit, & other units.

Design and setting: a descriptive cross sectional study was conducted in public sector hospital swat KPK Pakistan (saidu Group of teaching hospital, Nawaz sharif Kidney hospital)

Sample size and Sampling technique:

The Sample of the study was 160 according to the epidemiological calculator taking a confidence interval 5% and confidence level of 95%, While the sampling of this study was done by using a convenient sampling technique

Observations:

The observations of this study included the the extent of expertise, mindset, and implementation of nurses concerning medication safety, medications administration monitoring, and adverse drug reaction in public sector hospitals of swat, The factors that influence the nurses' adherence to the medication administration prerogatives, which are the appropriate recipient, accurate pharmaceutical, correct interval, suitable pathway, precise quantity, and proper documentations, The challenges and barriers that prevent the nurses from following the medication administration rights, such as workload, communication, documentation, education, etc. The outcomes and impacts of following or not following the medication administration rights on patient safety, quality of care, and professional accountability.

Questionnaire:

The questionnaire of this study was composed of four sections the first section of the questionnaire was about demographic data which only include age, gender, and place of work, years of experience, the second section was about the Medication Administration rights (Never, Once or Twice, Three or four times, More often) Fogarty and McKeon (2006), the third and fourth section included the Attitude of Nurses toward medication rights (Strongly disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly agree) and the Skills Checklist practice of nurses toward medication administrations rights (Met, Not Met) respectively. These sections comprise of total 36 questions distributed among nursing staff working in public sector hospitals of swat KPK Pakistan (SGHT, NSKH) as shown in Appendix 1.

The Nursing Internees were not included in this study since they don't have enough experience from the last 12 months and because their number in the hospital was not enough to be included in the study. The questionnaire contained questions relating to Knowledge, attitude, and practice regarding medications administration

Inclusion Criteria:

- All registered nurses Both male and females working in public sector hospitals swat [Saidu Group of Teaching Hospital Swat (Central and Saidu wings) Nawaz Sharif Kidney hospital (NSKH)].

Exclusion Criteria:

- Nurses working in administration side.
- Nursing Interns.
- Student Nurses

Data analysis.

The questionnaire has checked manually for missed values and inconsistency and then data has put in SPSS version 29 and descriptive statistics has used that include percentage and frequencies.

Summary.

In the current chapter, research methodology including study design, context of the investigation, investigation cohort, admission and elimination benchmarks, details of the data collection tool, interventional procedures, ethical approval, and plan for data analysis have been discussed in detail

Questionnaire results section 1

A questionnaire was adopted to assess the knowledge, attitude, & practice of nurses in

public sector hospitals of Swat District, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The results of the study are presented in the following sections. It was preferable to use descriptive methods, graphics, & charts to explain the acknowledgement of the nurses who took part in the research

The demographic Variables shown in Table no 1 shows the variable Age, Gender, years of experience, Level of education, and type of nursing unit.

Demographic Variables

Table no 1.

Variables	Options	Frequency	Percentage
Age	20-30	53	33.1
	30-40	86	53.8
	40-50	18	11.3
	50-55	3	1.9
Gender	Male	80	50%
	Female	80	50%
The highest level of education that a person has completed.	Diploma or General Nursing	28	17.5
	BS Nursing	74	46.3
	Master in Nursing	11	6.9
	Post RN	43	26.9
	Others	4	2.5
Years of experience	one to five years	47	29.4
	Five to ten years	62	38.8
	Ten to twenty years	47	29.4
	20-30 years	4	2.5

The study demographic variables were split into different categories. Age was divided into four groups. The largest group (53.8%) was aged 30-40, while 33.1% were aged 20-30, 11.3% were aged 40-50, and 1.9% were aged 50-55, the mean age of the sample was (33.13). Half (50%) of the participants were male and half (50%) were female. The majority (46.3%) had completed BS

Nursing, 26.9% had completed Post RN, 17.9% were Diploma or General Nursing, 6.9% had a Master's in Nursing, and 2.5% had completed other degrees. The majority of participants (38.8%) had between 5-10 years of experience, while 29.4% had between 1-5 years and 10-20 years respectively and 2.5% had between 20-30 years of experience.

Figure 1 Variable-Age of nurses (years)

From the figure 33% of the workforce were aged 20-30, while the majority (54%) were aged 30-40. The 40-50 age group made up 11%, and the smallest group was aged 50-55 (2%).

Figure 1.1 varibale Gender

The data indicates that out of 160 participants, half were male (50%) and half were female (50%)

Figure 1.2 Variable-Level of education of nurses

BS Nursing was completed by the majority of participants (46.3%). Post RN was completed by 26.9%, while 17.9% were Diploma or General Nursing, 6.9% had a Master's in Nursing, and 2.5% had completed other degrees.

Figure 1.3 Variable years of experience of nurses

The experience of the majority of the participants (39%) ranged from 5-10 years, while 29.4% had experience ranging from 1-5 years and 10-20 years, respectively. Only 2.5% of them had 20- 30 years of experience.

Questionnaire results section 2

Medication Administration- Errors

To the utmost extent of your understanding, within the past year, have you unintentionally committed any of the subsequent actions while administering medication?

Table no 2

Question	Options	Frequency	Percent
Given the wrong drug	Never	128	80.0%
	Once or twice	29	18.1%
	three or four times	3	1.9%
	Most of the time	---	---
By the wrong route	Never	133	83.1%
	Once or twice	24	15.0%
	three or four times	1	0.6%
	Most of the time	---	---
To the wrong patient	Never	133	83.1%
	Once or twice	21	13.1%
	three or four times	6	3.8%
	Most of the time	---	---
At the wrong time	Never	118	73.8%
	Once or twice	31	19.4%
	three or four times	9	5.6%
	Most of the time	1	0.6%
At the wrong dose	Never	104	65.0%
	Once or twice	43	26.9%
	three or four times	10	6.3%
	Most of the time	3	1.9%

This table shows how frequently a wrong drug, route, patient, time, or dose was given. Most of the participants have never been given the wrong drug, route, or patient. However, some participants have been given the wrong drug once or twice, three or four times, or most of the time. the most common type of drug error is reported by the nurse was giving the wrong dose, which occurred once or twice for 26.9% of participants, three or four times for 6.3%, and most of the time for 1.9%, followed by giving the drug administered inappropriately in terms of timing,

medication, administration route, and patient identification. The majority of the nurses (more than 65%) reported never making any of these medication errors, which indicates a high level of adherence to the medication administration rights.

The most frequent category of drug error reported by the nurses was once or twice, which suggests that these errors were rare and isolated incidents, rather than systematic or habitual problems.

The least frequent category of medication errors

reported by the nurses was most of the time, which implies that these errors were very

uncommon and exceptional cases, possibly due to extreme circumstances or factors.

Figure 2

This chart displays the occurrence of nurses administering the incorrect medication to patients. Most nurses, 80%, have never made this mistake. A small portion, 18.1%, have done so once or twice. Only 1.9% have made this error three or four times.

Figure2.1

This chart shows the frequency of nurses administering drugs by the wrong route to patients. The majority of the nurses, 83.1%, have never or rarely done this. A smaller percentage, 15%, have done these three or four times. Only 0.6% have done this more than four times.

This chart shows the frequency of nurses giving drugs to the wrong patient. The majority of the nurses, 83.1%, have never done this. A smaller percentage, 13.1%, have done this three or four times. Only 3.8% have done this more than four times.

This chart shows the frequency of nurses giving

drugs at the wrong time to patients. The majority of the nurses, 73.8%, have never done this. A smaller percentage, 19.4%, have done this three or four times.

Only 6.2% have done this more often.

This chart shows the frequency of nurses giving drugs at the wrong dose to patients. The majority of the nurses, 65%, have never done this. A smaller percentage, 26.9%, have done these three or four times.

Only 8.2% have done this once, twice or more often.

Questionnaire results section 2.1

Medication Administration - Noncompliance

Please specify the frequency with which you have had to deviate from the established guidelines in the past year when administering medication

Table no 3

Question	Options	Frequency	Percent
Did not verify with a doctor, an order that was illegible, unclear, incomplete, or that seemed inappropriate or unreasonable for the patient.	Never	74	46.3%
	some time	58	36.3%
	often	12	7.5%
	frequently	8	5.0%
	most of the time	8	5.0%
Did not obtain the proper authority (e.g., order from a doctor or signed protocol).	Never	66	41.3%
	some time	54	33.8%
	often	21	13.1%
	frequently	7	4.4%
	most of the time	12	7.5%
Did not complete appropriate documentation.	Never	70	43.8%
	some time	49	30.6%
	often	20	12.5%
	frequently	8	5.0%
	most of the time	13	8.1%
Did not verify a verbal/telephone order and its transcription according to hospital policy.	Never	75	46.9%
	some time	52	32.5%
	often	15	9.4%
	frequently	9	5.6%
	most of the time	9	5.6%
Did not check reference material (e.g., MIMS) when unsure about or unfamiliar with medication.	Never	69	43.1%
	some time	42	26.3%
	often	22	13.8%
	frequently	18	11.3%
	most of the time	9	5.6%
Did not check for allergies or previous	Never	56	35.0%
	some time	56	35.0%
	often	16	10.0%
	frequently	12	7.5%
	most of the time	20	12.5%
Did not monitor the effects of the drug after administration	Never	69	43.1%
	some time	47	29.4%
	often	21	13.1%
	frequently	11	6.9%
	most of the time	12	7.5%

Did not record/report side or adverse effects.	Never	60	37.5%
	some time	49	30.6%
	often	24	15.0%
	frequently	15	9.4%
	most of the time	12	7.5%
Did not check with a doctor before changing the route of administration.	Never	62	38.8%
	some time	47	29.4%
	often	25	15.6%
	frequently	14	8.8%
	most of the time	12	7.5%
Did not check the patient's identity.	Never	74	46.3%
	some time	42	26.3%
	often	20	12.5%
	frequently	10	6.3%
	most of the time	14	8.8%
Did not check the patient's chart.	Never	73	45.6%
	some time	36	22.5%
	often	20	12.5%
	frequently	18	11.3%
	most of the time	13	8.1%
Did not give relevant education and information to the patient (e.g., information sheet and/or clear expectation of procedure, side-effects, etc.)	Never	58	36.3%
	some time	46	28.7%
	often	26	16.3%
	frequently	16	10.0%
	most of the time	14	8.8%
Did not observe the patient taking the medication.	Never	60	37.5%
	some time	46	28.7%
	often	18	11.3%
	frequently	21	13.1%
	most of the time	15	9.4%

The table shows that a significant percentage of respondents have not followed proper medication administration rules. Some of the most frequent non-compliant actions include not verifying with a doctor, obtaining proper authority, completing appropriate documentation, verifying a verbal/telephone order, and checking reference material. Additionally, many respondents did not check for allergies or previous medication use and did not follow up on the drug's effects post-administration. These non-compliant actions can be dangerous and lead to errors in medication administration. It is

important to follow proper rules and procedures to ensure patient safety and accurate medication administration. Based on table the there are some observations below.

The most common rule that was bent by the respondents was not confirming with a doctor regarding an order that was unreadable, ambiguous, incomplete, or appeared unsuitable for the patient. This was done at least some time by 53.7% of the respondents.

The least common rule that was bent by the respondents was not checking reference material when unsure about or unfamiliar with

medication. This was done at least some time by 56.9% of the respondents. The rule that had the highest frequency of frequent or most-of-the-time bending was not checking for allergies or previous adverse reactions. This was done at least frequently by 20% of the respondents.

The rule that had the lowest frequency of frequent or most of the time-bending was not confirming a verbal/phone order and its transcription in accordance with hospital policy.. This was done at least frequently by 11.3% of the respondents.

The rule that had the highest variation in the responses was not checking for allergies or previous adverse reactions. The frequency of never and sometimes bending this rule was the same at 35%, while the frequency of most of the time-bending this rule was the highest at 12.5%.

The rule that had the lowest variation in the responses was failing to consult a doctor regarding an order that was difficult to read, unclear, or incomplete, or appeared unsuitable or unreasonable for the patient. The frequency of

never bending this rule was the highest at 46.3%, while the frequency of most of the time-bending this rule was the lowest at 5%.

The rule that had the most balanced distribution of responses was not checking the patient's identity. The frequency of never bending this rule was 46.3%, while the frequency of some time, often, frequently, and most of the time-bending this rule was 26.3%, 12.5%, 6.3%, and 8.8%, respectively.

The rule that had the most skewed distribution of responses was not checking reference material when unsure about or unfamiliar with medication. The frequency of never bending this rule was 43.1%, while the frequency of some time, often, frequently, and most of the time-bending this rule was 26.3%, 13.8%, 11.3%, and 5.6%, respectively.

Questionnaire results section 3

The attitude of Nurses towards medication rights.

Table no 4

Question	Options	Frequency	Percent
Medication errors do not need to be reported if detected before reaching the patient.	Never	79	49.4%
	some time	30	18.8%
	Often	15	9.4%
	Frequently	29	18.1%
	most of the time	7	4.4%
Information I disclose when reporting a medication error will be confidential.	Never	48	30.0%
	some time	45	28.1%
	often	18	11.3%
	frequently	41	25.6%
	most of the time	8	5.0%
It is not my responsibility to report medication errors caused by someone else.	Never	66	41.3%
	some time	47	29.4%
	Often	21	13.1%
	Frequently	16	10.0%
	most of the time	9	5.6%
I prefer to educate people who make medication errors rather than report the errors	Never	42	26.3%
	some time	44	27.5%
	Often	23	14.4%
	frequently	36	22.5%
	most of the time	15	9.4%

I fear being blamed if I report a medication error made.	Never	49	30.6%
	some time	47	29.4%
	Often	28	17.5%
	Frequently	29	18.1%
	most of the time	7	4.4%
I do not hesitate before I decide to report a medication error	Never	50	31.3%
	some time	28	17.5%
	Often	29	18.1%
	Frequently	35	21.9%
	most of the time	18	11.3%

The table shows the results of a survey that asked nurses about their attitudes towards medication rights, which are the principles that guide safe and effective medication administration. The survey had six questions, each with five options: never, some time, often, frequently and most of the time. The table shows the frequency and percent of nurses who chose each option for each question.

Based on the table there are some observations:

- Most nurses (49.4%) think that medication errors do not need to be reported if detected before reaching the patient, while only 4.4% think that they need to be reported most of the time.
- Most nurses (30%) think that information they disclose when reporting a medication error

will not be confidential, while only 5% think that it will be confidential most of the time.

- Most nurses (41.3%) think that it is not their responsibility to report medication errors caused by someone else, while only 5.6% think that it is their responsibility most of the time.
- Most nurses (26.3%) do not prefer to educate people who make medication errors rather than report the errors, while only 9.4% prefer to educate most of the time.
- Most nurses (30.6%) do not fear being blamed if they report a medication error they made, while only 4.4% fear being blamed most of the time.
- Most nurses (31.3%) do not hesitate before they decide to report a medication error, while only 11.3% hesitate most of the time.

Medication errors do not need to be reported if detected before reaching the patient

Figure 3.8

This chart shows the results of a survey that asked health care professionals how they feel about reporting medication errors that are detected before reaching the patient. The most of the people who responded. (71%) either disagree or strongly disagree with the that medication errors don't have to be reported if caught before reaching the patient., indicating that they believe that all medication errors should be reported regardless

of the outcome. However, 20% of the people who responded either agree or strongly agree with this statement., indicating that they believe that some medication errors can be ignored if they are corrected before harming the patient. The remaining 10% are neutral on this issue. This suggests that there is a significant variation in how health care professionals define and report medication errors.

INFORMATION I DISCLOSE WHEN REPORTING A MEDICATION ERROR WILL BE CONFIDENTIAL.

Figure 3.9

This chart shows the results of a survey that asked health care professionals how confident they are that the information they disclose when reporting a medication error will be confidential. The majority of the respondents (58.1%) either strongly agree or agree with this, while 25.6% are neutral and 16.3% either disagree or strongly disagree

It is not my responsibility to report medication errors caused by someone else

Figure 4.0

This Chart shows the result of a survey that asked health care professionals how they feel about reporting drug errors that are the result of another individual's actions. The majority of the Nurses (70.7%) most of the subject either strongly dissent or dissent with the statement that it is not

their obligation to report these errors., while 13.1% are neutral and 16.2% either agree or strongly agree. Only 0.6% chose the option of "I don't know". This suggests that most health care professionals feel accountable for reporting medication errors regardless of who caused them

Figure 4.1

This chart shows the result of a survey that asked healthcare professionals how they feel about educating individuals who commit medication errors instead of disclosing the errors.. The majority of the respondents (54%) either disagree or strongly disagree with this statement, while 23% agree & 14% are neutral. Only 9% strongly agree with this statement. This suggests that most healthcare professionals do not prefer to use medication errors as an opportunity for learning and improvement, but rather as a matter of accountability and responsibility.

I FEAR BEING BLAMED IF I REPORT A MEDICATION ERROR I MADE.

Figure 4.2

This chart shows the result of a survey that asked health care professionals how they feel about being blamed if they report a medication error they made. The majority of the study participants (45%) either disagree or strongly disagree with this statement, indicating that they do not fear being blamed for their errors. However, 31% of

the respondents either agree or strongly agree with this statement, indicating that they do fear being blamed for their errors. The remaining 24% are neutral on this issue. This suggests that there is a significant variation in how health care professionals perceive the consequences of reporting medication errors.

I do not hesitate before I decide to report a medication error

Figure 4.3

This chart shows the results of a survey that asked health care professionals how they feel about reporting medication errors. The majority of the respondents (43%) either agree or strongly agree with the statement that they do not hesitate before they decide to report a medication error, indicating that they are confident and comfortable with the reporting process. However,

49% of the respondents either disagree or strongly disagree with this statement, indicating that they have some hesitation or reluctance to report medication errors. The remaining 18% are neutral on this issue. This suggests that there is a significant variation in how health care professionals approach the reporting of medication errors.

Questionnaire results section 3

the Skills Checklist practice of nurses toward medication administrations rights (Met, Not Met) table no 5

Question	Options	Frequency	Percentage
Check the accuracy of the medication order. (check Medication Administration Record with prescriber orders)	Met	137	85.6
	Not Met	21	13.1
Assess for any contraindications to client receiving medications (NPO, hypotension, heart rate, allergies, labs, etc.)	Met	121	75.6
	Not Met	39	24.4
Perform the 6 rights of medication administration a) patient (verbal, ID: name and mr#) b) drug/indication c) dose (including correct computation) d) route e) time f) documentation	Met	124	77.5
	Not Met	35	21.9
Med knowledge: a) Generic and trade names b) Classification (non critical) c) Indication including your patients d) Therapeutic dose range and your pt dose e) Significant side effects f) Nursing implications	Met	121	75.6
	Not Met	37	23.1
Prepare Medications a) Wash hands b) Check each medication against Medication Administration Record. c) Check medication expiration date d) Prepare IVPB: I. Inject appropriate medication into appropriate solution (if necessary) II. Attach IV tubing and prim Never leaves medication unattended	Met	120	75.0
	Met	39	24.4
Document according to policy and procedure	Met	115	71.9
	Not Met	45	28.1
	Met	119	74.4
	Not Met	41	25.6

This table shows the results of a survey on the skills checklist practice of nurses toward

medication administration rights. It has seven questions and two options (Met or Not Met) for

each question. The table also shows the frequency and percentage of responses for each option.

Some possible observations from the table are:

- The question with the highest percentage of Met responses (85.6%) is “Check the accuracy of the medication order”.
- The question with the lowest percentage of Met responses (71.9%) is “Never leaves medication unattended”.
- The question with the highest percentage of Not Met responses (28.1%) is also “Never leaves medication unattended”.
- The question with the lowest percentage of Not Met responses (13.1%) is “Check the accuracy of the medication order”.
- The average percentage of Met responses across all questions is 76.4%.
- The average percentage of Not Met responses across all questions is 23.6%.

DISCUSSION

Introduction.

This chapter will analyze and interpret the results of this study. It will discuss the findings in relation to the research questions or objectives, it will provide explanations, insights, and interpretations of the data collected. It will also involve comparing the findings with previous research, identifying patterns or trends, and discussing the implications and limitations of the study. Overall, this chapter will provide a deeper understanding of the research findings and their significance.

The aim of this study was to assess the Knowledge attitude and practice regarding medication administration rights among nurses and to identify the barriers that prevent them from reporting MAEs. This is an important aspect of improving patient safety, as safe drug administration is a high priority for all healthcare professionals, especially nurses. Examining the nurses’ practices in handling medication administration and MAEs and their reporting behaviors of such errors could be the first step to prevent the same mistakes from happening again in the future. Many studies from different countries have shown the problem of

reporting/under-reporting MAEs among nurses,[1-28] but this is the first study to evaluate Knowledge attitude and practice regarding medication administration rights among nurses working in public sector hospitals of swat Pakistan, as far as we know.

The importance of patient safety in health care practice, especially in nursing and medicine, is widely recognized around the world. (24) Patient safety can be simply defined as avoiding errors and harmful effects that may occur to patients during health care, according to WHO (2017). A major part of the clinical nurse’s role is administering medication(9). Medication errors account for 33% of all hospital injuries, and 30% of those errors reported to the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in 2013 were fatal FDA. (26) Nurses have to make a professional judgment and use their safety skills when giving any medication, acting in the best interests of the patient. Nurses are the closest professionals to the patient and the last link in the chain of medication administration. (27)

A narrative literature review suggests that medication errors make up between 12% and 20% of all errors, and these errors have a high cost in terms of human, economic, and social aspects. (28)

Section 1st: Socio-demographic characteristics of the studied participants:

The finding of the present study indicated that the study demographic variables were split into different categories. Age was divided into four groups. It indicated that the majority (53.8%) of the participant was aged 30-40, and the mean age of the participant was (33.13). Half (50%) of the participants were male and half (50%) were female this is contradicted by the study done at Mansoura University Hospitals. [14] who reported that the majority of participants were female. This can be attributed to the fact that both male and female individuals, particularly nurses in middle age, are more exposed to the concept of medication errors due to their responsibility in medication administration.

Regarding the educational level, the current study provided clarification that The majority (46.3%)

had completed BS Nursing while 26.9% had completed Post RN, with a similar study conducted in Jordan reported that most of the nurses were having BS nursing degrees. [19] This could be attributed to increasing knowledge level and improved medication administration practices.

Regarding years of experience, the present study revealed that the majority of participants (38.8%) had between 5-10 years of experience, while 29.4% had between 1-5 years of experience which is similar to the study conducted in Ethiopia with 90% of nurses had less than 10 years of experience. [28] This factor can affect the quality of care given to patients, as well as the job performance for medication administration. This is because Senior staff may have more clinical practice experience than new or junior staff members, who may face difficulties with various methods of giving medication.

Section 2nd: Nurses' knowledge regarding medication administration rights:

Safe medication administration requires knowledge of pharmacology, specifically knowing the right drug. In hospital settings, medication errors are the most common type of error. [14] Nurses need effective pharmacological knowledge for various reasons since they are the primary healthcare professionals responsible for medication administration.[29] So it is clearly important to keep updating the knowledge and learning new things in this field.

Therefore, this study aims to assess nurses' knowledge regarding medication administration rights. The study looks at the basic knowledge of medication administration rights, knowledge of the right drugs, the right route, the right patient, the dose, the right time, and the right documentation. It also looks at the percentage that how much nurses have violated these rights and the percentage of medication administration errors (MAEs) and medication administration non-compliance.

The current study revealed that Most of nurses never gave the wrong drug, route, or patient. But some nurses gave the wrong drug a few times,

several times, or often. The most common mistake the nurses made was giving the wrong dose, which happened a few times for 26.9% of nurses, several times for 6.3%, and often for 1.9%, followed by giving the drug at the wrong time, the wrong drug, by the wrong route, and to the wrong patient. Most of the nurses (over 65%) said they never made any of these mistakes, which shows a high level of following the rules for giving medication. The most usual number of mistakes the nurses said they made was a few times, which means that these mistakes were not common and regular, but rare and random.

The least usual number of mistakes the nurses said they made was often, which means that these mistakes were very rare and unusual, maybe because of very hard or different situations or reasons. This research also found that Most nurses (78.6%) have good knowledge about medication rights and 22.4% of nurses made a medication error in the Lat 12 months means they have poor knowledge of medication administration rights, the mean score of good knowledge and poor knowledge of medication administration rights and roles was

- Given the wrong drug: 4.69
- By the wrong route: 4.82
- To the wrong patient: 4.79
- At the wrong time: 4.64
- At the wrong dose: 4.44

The total mean score is 4.68, which is close to 5 (Never). This means that the nurses have a high level of knowledge overall about medication administration rights and roles. These findings are contradicted by a study conducted in Jordan, which found that two-thirds (66.67) of nurses have poor total knowledge scores regarding medication administration. The reason for this result might be the presence of training and a high level of education among the majority of the nurses (78.6%) in this study who hold a bachelor's degree in nursing.

These findings are comparative to a study conducted in Ethiopia, the prevalence of medication administration errors (MAEs) among nurses was 68.1% in the previous 12 months,

which is higher than this research finding of 22.4%¹. The most common types of MAEs in that study were wrong time (38.9%), wrong dose (26.6%), and wrong drug (17.7%), which are similar to this research findings.^[30] To avoid errors, nurses should know the purpose, effect, limitation, side effects, and interaction of drugs. ^[31] Therefore, it is essential to assess the level of knowledge about medication administration to identify and address the weakness and ensure high-quality care.

Section 3rd: Nurses' attitude regarding medication administration rights.

Nurses should have a positive attitude toward medication administration to make medication administration safe. It is very important to know how nurses respond toward medication administration because a negative attitude affects how nurses act in all the steps of medication administration. Reporting errors is easier when attitudes are positive because being afraid of how managers and peers will react to medication errors shows a bad attitude. ^[32] This result was contradicted by what the current study found, as the current study showed that (54.2%) have a positive attitude toward reporting errors, while (45.8%) have a negative attitude regarding medication error reporting. This may be due to having enough information and also may be because of a manageable workload that allows the nurse to pay more attention to other roles assigned to them.

Furthermore, some nurses think medication errors should not be reported especially if they work in a place where people are reprimanded for making mistakes which will make error reporting less and make hiding mistakes more, finally making it hard to find errors and to stop them from happening.

A comparative study to this research found that Most of the sample show a positive attitude about giving medication and try to avoid errors by following preventive steps, such as regular training, using reliable guidelines based on scientific proof, constantly assessing their clinical abilities, and reporting errors to improve care. ^[28] These findings indicate that there were

positive attitudes among the participants.

Section 4th: Nurses' practice regarding medication administration rights

Giving medication safely involves more than just prescribing it. Nurses must follow proper steps to ensure safe administration.

In relation to this, the present study shows that More than three-quarters (76.4%) of the nurses have good practice and follow proper administration skills. However, (23.6%) have poor practice and do not follow proper skills, this finding is supported by a similar study by Al-Momani et al. (2020) that assessed nurses in Jordan, The study found that 75% of the nurses had high practice and 25% had low practice of medication administration. The study recommended that nurses should receive continuous education and training on medication administration to improve their knowledge and practice.^[33]

Generally, the current study revealed that the mean percent score of nurses' knowledge was 4.68, which is close to 5 (Never). This means that the nurses have high level of knowledge overall about medication administration rights and roles. Additionally, more than three quarter (76.4%) of the nurses have good practice and follow proper administration skills. However, (23.6%) have poor practice and do not follow proper skills. Moreover, the current study also showed that (54.2%) have a positive attitude toward reporting errors, while (45.8%) have a negative attitude regarding medication error reporting.

These findings are encouraging; it indicates that improvement in the patient's well-being could potentially be improved through the process of medication administration. Therefore, errors in medication administration can be reduced by nurses.

Recommendation

The study suggests that Nurses should obtain comprehensible materials such as booklets and brochures that elucidate how to administer medicines accurately and avert medication errors. These materials should be accessible in all locations where nurses operate.

The study also recommends that Nursing students should acquire knowledge about how to utilize evidence-based protocols for dispensing medicines in their pharmacology courses.

A consistent sheet should be employed to appraise the knowledge, attitude, and practices of nurses about the caliber of medication administration.

A policy that fosters reporting medication errors without dread of punishment should be instituted.

Training and education sessions should be provided as part of the continual training program.

Conclusions

Most nurses have good knowledge, practice, and a positive attitude toward medication administration rights. However, some nurses had poor practice and a negative attitude toward reporting errors, which needs to be improved by continuous education, training, experience, reduced workload, and positive organizational culture. Overall, the study concludes that medication administration plays a crucial role in improving patient well-being and reducing errors.

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Annexes

Annexures 1

List of Abbreviations		
1	APRNs	Advanced Practice Registered Nurses.
2	BSN	Bachelor of science in Nursing
3	FDA	Food and drug authority
4	GN	General Nursing
5	HAMs	High alert medications
6	ICU	Intensive care unit
7	ID	identification

8	IVPB	Intravenous Piggyback
9	KPK	Khyber pukhonkhwa
10	KP-BOIT	
12	MAE	Medication administrtaion error
12	MANC	Medication administration noncompliance
13	MARs	Medication administration Rights
14	MIMS	Medical Information Management System
15	MSN	Master in Nursing
16	MR no	Medical record number
17	NCBI	National Center for Biotechnology Information.
18	NPO	Nothing per oral
29	NSKH	Nawaz sharif kidney hospital
20	SGTH	Saidu group of teaching hospital
21	SPSS	Statistical Package for the Social Sciences
22	WHO	World health organization

Annexure 2 questionnaire for nurses

Surveyor: Mujahid Ullah

Royal College of Nursing, Khyber Medical University Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Pakistan.

Medication Administration Questionnaire
Fogarty and McKeon (2006) Medication Administration Questionnaire - Errors

1.1 Background

This scale was developed with the assistance of subject matter experts. The items were based on the ‘five rights’, that is, the guidelines traditionally taught to all nurses regarding medication administration: ‘the right patient, the right drug, the right dose, the right route, and the right time’. These ‘five rights’ have been referred to as the ritual that nurses should use to prevent medication errors in nursing.

1.2 Instructions and Questions

To be completed by registered nurses and enrolled nurses with medication endorsement who are currently involved in medication administration.

In this section, we are seeking your support to discover what is happening in the hospital system that is contributing to medication errors. Research indicates that medication errors are common. Research in other complex industries has found that the system in which people work has an impact on their performance, and when conditions in the organisation are improved, the number of errors decreases.

Your responses will NOT be available to anyone EXCEPT the researchers at the University of Southern Queensland and you are assured that they will be treated as strictly confidential. To ensure anonymity, the results will be reported for the District as a whole and not by individual hospitals or sections within hospitals.

To the best of your knowledge, in the last **12 months**, have you ever mistakenly done any of the following when administering a medication?

		Never	Once or Twice	Three or four times	More often
1.	Given the wrong drug	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	By the wrong route	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	To the wrong patient	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	At the wrong time	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	At the wrong dose	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If you wish, please comment on what you believe may have contributed to the above.	
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1. Medication Administration Questionnaire – Noncompliance

1.1 Background

This scale was designed to capture generic violation behaviours based on nursing competencies and to include only those behaviours directly under the control of the nurse administering the medication. That is, it excludes doctors’ behaviours. The scale was developed with the assistance of subject matter experts, that is, nurses with many years of experience in medication administration, and with reference to the procedures required for safe medication administration.

1.2 Instructions and Items

In this section, we want to know if it is necessary for you to “bend the rules” to get your job done. Medication administration involves following guidelines that are in place to maintain quality outcomes. However, because of conditions in the workplace (for example, workload, unavailability of doctors, impractical procedures, etc), it may not always be possible to follow all the rules. Again, you are assured that your responses will be treated as STRICTLY CONFIDENTIAL, with the results being reported for the District as a whole and not by individual hospitals or sections within hospitals.

Annexures 3

IV Medication Administration Skills Checklist

Student: _____ Validator: _____ Date: _____

Medication: _____,

Criteria	Met	Not Met	Comment
1) Check the accuracy of the medication order. (check Medication Administration Record with prescriber orders)			
2) Assess for any contraindications to client receiving medications (NPO, hypotension, heart rate, allergies, labs, etc.)			
3) Perform the 6 rights of medication administration a) patient (verbal, ID: name and mr#) b) drug/indication c) dose (including correct computation) d) route e) time f) documentation			
4) Med knowledge: a) Generic and trade names b) Classification (non critical) c) Indication including your patients d) Therapeutic dose range and your pt dose e) Significant side effects f) Nursing implications			

<p>5) Prepare meds</p> <p>a) Wash hands</p> <p>b) Check each medication against Medication Administration Record.</p> <p>c) Check medication expiration date</p> <p>d) Prepare IVPB:</p> <p>i) Inject appropriate medication into appropriate solution (if necessary)</p> <p>ii) Attach IV tubing and prime without losing medication and expelling air</p> <p>iii) Wear gloves if antibiotic</p> <p>e) Take medications/ Medication Administration Record to patient's room</p> <p>f) Assesses IV access for patency &/or complications</p> <p>g) Ask patient name, check arm band for name and mr#</p> <p>h) Tell patient name, dose, indication as appropriate</p> <p>i) Attach IVPB (if hep lock must flush with normal saline first)</p> <p>j) Adjust flow rate/set pump</p> <p>k) Document on Medication Administration Record and I&O</p> <p>l) Medication runs "on time" and is discontinued and discarded.</p>			
<p>6) Never leaves medication unattended</p>			
<p>7) Document according to policy and procedure</p>			

Please indicate how often in the past 12 months you have had to bend the rules in the following ways when administering a medication:

		Never	Sometimes	Often	Frequently	Most of the time
1.	Did not verify with a doctor, an order that was illegible, unclear, incomplete, or that seemed inappropriate or unreasonable for the patient.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2.	Did not obtain the proper authority (e.g., order from doctor or signed protocol).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3.	Did not complete appropriate documentation.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4.	Did not verify a verbal/telephone order and its transcription according to hospital policy.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5.	Did not check reference material (e.g., MIMS) when unsure about or unfamiliar with medication.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
6.	Did not check for allergies or previous adverse reactions.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

7.	Did not monitor the effects of the drug after administration.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
8.	Did not record/report side or adverse effects.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
9.	Did not check with a doctor before changing the route of administration.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
10.	Did not check the patient's identity.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
11.	Did not check the patient's chart.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
12.	Did not give relevant education and information to the patient (e.g., information sheet and/or clear expectation of procedure, side-effects, etc.)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
13.	Did not observe the patient taking the medication.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	If you wish, please comment on what you believe may have contributed to the above					

Annexures 4

Attitude of Nurses towards medication rights.

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
Medication errors do not need to be reported if detected before reaching the patient.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Information I disclose when reporting a medication error will be confidential.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
It is not my responsibility to report medication errors caused by someone else.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I prefer to educate people who make medication errors rather than report the errors.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I fear being blamed if I report a medication error I made.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I do not hesitate before I decide to report a medication error	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Annexures 5 Consent Form

Annexures 6 Approval letters

Institution Royal College Of Nursing Swat , Marghazar Road, Saidu Sharif, Swat, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.						
Knowledge attitude and practice regarding medication administration rights among nurses working in public sector hospitals of swat Pakistan						
Budget amount: In Pakistani rupees						
S.nu	Description	Quantity	Unit	Cost	Sub-Total	Remarks
01	Inform consent	320	1	6/ page	1920	
02	Questionnaire	320	3	6/page	5760	
03	Travel cost	Per trip	12	1000	12000	
04	Thesis binding and stationary	ONCE	1	1	5000	
05	Miscellaneous Charges				15000	
11	Grand total				40000	

Annexures 7 Budget Plan

Annexures 8
Gant Chart

	June 2023				July 2023				August 2023				September 2023			
	w1	w2	w3	w4	w5	w6	w7	w8	w9	w10	w11	w12	w13	w14	w15	w16
Proposal Submission		█	█													
Approval from GC				█												
Approval from ASRB					█											
Data collection						█	█									
Data Analysis						█	█									
Drafting Chapter I							█									
Drafting Chapter II								█	█							
Drafting Chapter III										█	█					
Drafting Chapter IV, V, VI											█	█				
Compilation of Thesis													█	█		
Thesis Defense															█	

